

one-fourth of ΔH_g . D(Cu—Cu), the copper-copper bond dissociation energy in dimeric complexes is estimated as described in the literature⁶.

The metal-oxoligand mean bond dissociation energy is higher for copper(II) propionate than that of the acetate or the formate depending upon ligand field strength.

References

1. B. N. FIGGIS and R. L. MARTIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 3837; R. TSUCHIDA and S. YAMADA, *Nature (London)*, 1955, 176, 1171.
2. R. L. MARTIN and H. WATERMAN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 1359; M. KATO, H. B. JONASSEN and J. C. FANNING, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, 64, 99.
3. A. F. TROTMAN-DICKENSON, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", Pergamon, Oxford, 1975, Vol. 3, p. 54.
4. N. A. LANGE, "Handbook of Chemistry," 13th. ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, 1986.
5. P. M. BURKINSHAW and C. T. MORTIMER, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1983, 48, 101.
6. J. A. CONNOR, *Top. Curr. Chem.*, 1971, 71, 71.

Potentiometric Studies of some Trivalent Rare Earth Complexes with *p*-Sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene Anil

P. SANYAL, N. N. GHOSH and G. P. SENGUPTA*

Department of Chemistry, Visva-Bharati University,
Santiniketan-731 235

Manuscript received 21 June 1989, revised 29 January 1990,
accepted 3 July 1990

THE present communication deals with pH-metric determination of formation constants of complexes of *p*-sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil with Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} using Bjerrum-Calvin^{1,2} pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti³. The study was carried out in aqueous medium at 25, 35 and 45° at constant ionic strength.

Experimental

The Schiff base ligand *p*-sulphono-2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil was prepared by sulphonation of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene anil using the reported method⁴. All other chemicals were either of A.R. grade or purified before use. Rare earth metals were converted to perchlorates and were estimated by EDTA method⁵.

Concentrations of reactants used were 0.02 *M* acid, 0.1 *M* NaClO₄, 0.004 *M* ligand and 0.001 *M* metal salt. Total volume in each case was 50 ml. An ECIL 5651 digital pH-meter with combined glass electrode was used for pH measurement in titrations against standard alkali.

Results and Discussion

The $\bar{n}_H$ values extend over the range, $0.35 < \bar{n}_H < 1.94$ which indicates a two-step deprotonation for the ligand. The proton-ligand constants, K_1^H and K_2^H correspond to the deprotonation of the phenolic hydroxyl attached to the naphthaldehyde moiety and sulphonic acid⁶ group, respectively.

$\bar{n}$ values for Nd^{III} were in the range, $0 < \bar{n} < 2$ and for Pr^{III}, Sm^{III} and Gd^{III} it was $0 < \bar{n} < 1$. Appearance of precipitate at $\bar{n} > 1$ prevented calculation of second step stability constant for these metal ions. It was observed that with increase in temperature the metal ligand stability constant decreases.

The order of stability ($\log K_1$) was Pr^{III} < Nd^{III} > Sm^{III} > Gd^{III}. Such stability order (Table 1) is not uncommon^{7,8} in the case of lanthanides.

The values of ΔG , ΔS and ΔH for complexation reactions have been evaluated by standard expressions⁹ (Table 1). The enthalpy terms are favourable for complexation. The entropy terms for the complexes are negative and hence unfavourable and suggests that the primary hydration sphere of the interacting ions are retained to some extent.

References

1. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Haase, Copenhagen, 1941.
2. M. CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003.

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT 35°

Cations	I = 0.1 <i>M</i> (NaClO ₄)		35°		45°		- ΔG kcal mol ⁻¹	- ΔH kcal mol ⁻¹	- ΔS cal K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2			
H ⁺	9.25	4.50	8.50	4.45	8.00	4.70			
Pr ^{III}	7.60	—	7.10	—	6.20	—	10.00	34.27	78.79
Nd ^{III}	8.05	6.20	7.80	5.40	7.00	4.20	10.99	70.83	194.29
Sm ^{III}	6.80	—	6.25	—	4.85	—	8.80	45.70	119.77
Gd ^{III}	6.10	—	5.55	—	4.15	—	7.82	47.98	130.39

3. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; 1953, 3397.
4. A. K. MUKHERJEE and P. RAY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 32, 633.
5. G. SCHWARZENBACH, "Complexometric Titrations", Methuen, London, 1956, p. 60.
6. G. P. SENGUPTA and C. R. BERA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, 43, 2139.
7. F. H. SPEEDING, J. E. POWEL and J. E. W. WRIGHT, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 34; J. SCHWARZENBACH and R. GUT, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1956, 39, 1589; R. C. VICKREY, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.*, 1956, 2, 308.
8. L. K. A. STAVELY and T. RANDELL, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 26, 157.
9. K. B. YATSMIRSKII and V. P. VASELOV, "Instability Constants of Complex Compound", Pergamon, Oxford, 1960, p. 63.

Kinetic Parameters from TG Analysis of Copper-Pyrrole-2-thiocarboxamide Complex

J. P. SRIVASTAVA, V. KUMAR* and A. P. SINHA

Department of Chemistry, Magadh University,
Bodh Gaya-824 234

Manuscript received 31 July 1989, revised 8 March 1990,
accepted 19 June 1990

THE rate of thermal decomposition is determined by the rate of one or more of these stages. Sometimes the rate-determining stage at the beginning of the pyrolysis may lose its significance and later another stage can take its place.

The decomposition rate of a TG curve can be defined as $-d\alpha/dt$, where α stands for the fraction of the initial compound undergoing reaction. In isothermal conditions it may be presumed that the reaction rate is dependent only to the fraction reacted,

$$-\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K\alpha^n$$

where n is the order of reaction and K the specific rate constant. The specific rate constant depends upon the temperature by the expression,

$$K = A.e^{-E/RT}$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor, E the activation energy and R the gas constant.

Experimental

An electrobalance with a recorder operating at 1 mV full scale was used for obtaining the thermograms. A chromelalumel thermocouple placed 3–4 mm below the sample holder, the platinum boat (2 mm × 8 mm dia) was used for recording the sample temperature. A heating rate of 10° min⁻¹ was employed and chart speed was maintained at 600 mm h⁻¹. Calculations were carried out from

a single TG curve for the second stage of decomposition of the complex around 190°. The initial stage corresponded to the elimination of coordinated water.

Preparation of the sample : A green precipitate of copper complex corresponding to molecular formula CuL.H₂O was obtained by mixing the ethanolic solutions of the ligand with cupric chloride in the molar ratio of 1 : 1.

Results and Discussion

The kinetic parameter of the complex have been calculated by both Freeman and Carroll method and Zsako method.

Freeman and Carroll¹ suggested a linear relationship between $\Delta \log \frac{dw}{dt} / \Delta \log W_r$ and $\Delta T^{-1} / \Delta \log W_r$, where $W_r = (W_0 - W)$ and W_0 is weight loss at completion of reaction, W the total weight-loss upto time t and T the absolute temperature. The intercept $-x$ of the straight line plotted from the evaluated values for the equation indicates the order of reaction and the slope indicates the energy of activation E_a to $E_a/2.3R$. The reaction order and the activation energy of the compound have been evaluated as 1.0 and 35.69 kcal mol⁻¹ for the second transformation stage under consideration.

These values were compared with the method of Doyle² as modified by Zsako³. Doyle's equation for TG curve is

$$g(\alpha) = \frac{ZE_a}{Rq} p(x)$$

where Z is frequency factor, E_a the activation energy, R the gas constant and q the heating rate. The value $g(\alpha)$ is a certain function of α and

$$\alpha = \frac{W_0 - W}{W_0 - W_t}$$

where W , W_0 and W_t are the actual, initial and final weights of the sample respectively. The $g(\alpha)$ is calculated for various order of decomposition from the equation,

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = K(1 - \alpha)^b$$

where b is the order of reaction. For $b = 0$ $g_0(\alpha) = \alpha$, for $b = 1$, $g_1(\alpha) = \ln\left(\frac{1}{1 - \alpha}\right)$ and for $b = 2$,

$$g_2(\alpha) = \left(\frac{\alpha}{1 - \alpha}\right).$$

The values of B_0 , B_1 and B_2 have been calculated in the present case from the equations given herein with the help of the data for $g(\alpha)$ and $-\log p(x)$ at different temperatures. B_0 , B_1 and B_2 are the constancy of the difference $\log(\alpha) - \log p(x)$ for zero, first and second order reactions respectively, which provide information to suggest